

ADMAIORA

Grant Agreement number: 814413

Project acronym: ADMAIORA

Project title: ADvanced nanocomposite MAterIals fOr in situ treatment and
ultrASound-mediated management of osteoarthritis

Funding scheme: H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2018-2020

D 7.10

Report on 3rd ADMAIORA workshop and other key communication events

Due date of deliverable: [31/01/2022]

Actual submission date: [30/01/2022]

Start date of project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 49 months

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: [SSSA]

Deliverable author: [All]

Version: [3, Final]

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon 2020 Programme		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Service)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Service)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Service)	

Document History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of Main Changes
1	15/01/2022	Lorenzo Vannozi, Andrea Cafarelli, SSSA	First version of the template for project Deliverables
2	18/01/2022	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	Revision of the first draft and request for changes/integrations
3	30/01/2022	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	Final Deliverable version and submission

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	4
2	Introduction	5
3	Technical and non-technical Workshops within ADMAIORA.....	6
3.1	Symposium on “Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration”, 47th ESAO Congress – technical workshop	6
3.2	Live Webinar on Osteoarthritis and Arthritis organized by AMRER – non-technical workshop	9
4	Other key communication events	10
4.1	TV interview on SuperQuark – RAI: Italian State Broadcaster.....	10
4.2	ADMAIORA @ Olympic games of Tokyo 2021	11
4.3	TEDx Talk- LungarnoMediceo	11
5	Conclusions	13

1 Executive summary

This Deliverable describes the key dissemination and communication events organized in the third year of the ADMAIORA project, as devised in the preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. In particular, the second project-related **scientific symposium** was virtually held during the 47th European Society of Artificial Organs (ESAO) Congress by the Project Coordinator, which was postponed to 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

A **technical Workshop** was held in February 2021 by the Project Coordinator in collaboration with IOR, addressing clinical end-users, namely orthopedists, radiologists and other people interested in imaging and diagnostics. Here, the speakers discussed recent developments and potential future applications of diagnostic and therapeutic ultrasound for osteoarticular applications and beyond, highlighting the challenges yet to be addressed and the possible future impact of this technology, highlighting the links with the ADMAIORA project efforts. This workshop was already described in Deliverable D7.8.

A **non-technical Workshop** was held in October 2021, in which SSSA and IOR, in coordination with AMRER, an Italian association of rheumatic patients, promoted the project results to healthcare system actors, OA patients, and elderly people. The webinar was seen by approximately **2700 people**.

Finally, this Deliverable describes the following **additional key communication events**:

- A TV interview delivered by Prof. Ricotti to “SuperQuark”, a program transmitted on RAI: Italian State Broadcaster, on ADMAIORA and the new frontiers of regenerative medicine (**2.263.000 people reached**), available also on YouTube (**views: 11.800**);
- A Promotional video produced by the Italian Olympic Committee (CONI) and shared during the Olympic games 2021 held in Tokyo, also promoted on the CONI social networks;
- A TEDx talk (Lungarno Mediceo) in September 2021, delivered by Prof. Ricotti, available also on YouTube (views: **1580**).

2 Introduction

The dissemination plan, described in Deliverable D7.2 (Preliminary report of the preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plan), includes presentations at scientific and technological events. In particular, one Workshop per year dedicated to the ADMAIORA themes is foreseen to present the project results to a broad audience of potential users, stakeholders, and scientists. To this purpose, the Project Coordinator proposed a **symposium** focused on a scientific topic closely adherent to the ADMAIORA scope during the **47th European Society of Artificial Organs (ESAO) Congress** and the submitted proposal was accepted. The title of the event was "*Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration*" (see section 3.1). The workshop was virtually held at the 47th ESAO Congress last year.

According to Deliverable D7.2, within special communication activities, non-technical workshops and a communication event co-organized with CONI at the Olympic games of Tokyo 2020, were expected to be organized during all the project duration to communicate results to healthcare system actors and stakeholders. These events also serve to share with osteoarthritis (OA) patients and, in general elderly people, the technologies that are under development in the project, thus preventing possible barriers to the future adoption of the project results.

In this context, a non-technical workshop in the form of a live webinar organized by AMRER was held on 12 October 2021. On this occasion, within the webinar entitled "*Osteoarthritis and Arthritis*" clinicians and some SSSA and IOR components illustrated the current challenges in the treatment of osteoarthritis and replied to a general audience about specific questions on such a disease.

Furthermore, a technical Workshop on ultrasound and their applications was held on 19 February 2021 by SSSA in collaboration with IOR, addressing clinical end-users, such as orthopedists, radiologists, and other professionals interested in ultrasound-based imaging and diagnostics. During this workshop, entitled "*Ultrasuoni: l'innovazione dalla diagnostica alla terapia*", recent developments and potential future applications of diagnostic and therapeutic ultrasound for osteoarticular applications and beyond were discussed (full description in Deliverable D7.8).

Finally, this Deliverable describes the following key communication events:

- A TV interview delivered by Prof. Ricotti to "SuperQuark", a program transmitted on RAI: Italian State Broadcaster, on ADMAIORA and the new frontiers of regenerative medicine, available also on YouTube;
- A Promotional video produced by the Italian Olympic Committee (CONI) and shared during the Olympic games 2021 held in Tokyo, also promoted on the CONI social networks;
- A TEDx talk (Lungarno Mediceo) in September 2021, delivered by Prof. Ricotti, available also on YouTube.

3 Technical and non-technical Workshops within ADMAIORA

3.1 Symposium on “Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration”, 47th ESAO Congress – technical workshop

This Symposium was organized by Prof. Leonardo Ricotti as Chair, in collaboration with Prof. Sonia Fiorilli, Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy, as Co-Chair. This event was also designed to create synergies between two H2020 projects on the theme of regenerative medicine and funded in the same Call, namely ADMAIORA (<https://www.admaiora-project.com/>) and GIOTTO (<https://www.giottoproject.eu/>).

The Symposium was entitled “*Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissues regeneration*” and it touched themes related to osteoarticular tissues regeneration, stem cells, innovative biomaterials and smart devices.

The abstract of the Symposium is reported below:

“This Symposium tackles the theme of osteoarticular tissues regeneration, by presenting the most research efforts in this field, led by important European actors.

Stem cells, innovative biomaterials and smart devices enabling advanced functionalities and new therapeutic strategies will constitute the focus of this event, with the aim to solve unmet clinical challenges related to bone-related diseases (e.g. osteoporosis) and cartilage-related pathologies (e.g. osteoarthritis).

The keynote talk will analyze the variegated and interdisciplinary research domain of biomaterials for osteoarticular tissues regeneration. Then, the subsequent talks will provide an overview of cutting-edge research carried out in different ambitious projects funded by the European Community, which propose potentially ground-breaking solutions for cartilage and bone regeneration, bringing such innovation as close as possible to a future clinical translation.”

The overall duration of the Symposium was set to 90 minutes. One keynote speaker and four speakers were invited to give their presentation on themes related to the Symposium.

The final list of speakers is reported below:

Keynote Speaker:

Prof. **Luigi Ambrosio** (Institute of Polymers, Composites & Biomaterials, National Research Council, Naples, Italy)

Talk title: “Biomaterials for osteoarticular tissues regeneration: from basic research to the clinics”

Other speakers:

1. Prof. **Leonardo Ricotti** (The BioRobotics Institute, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Pisa, Italy)

Talk title: “Smart materials and ultrasound for cartilage healing: the ADMAIORA project” (<https://www.admaiora-project.com/>)

2. Prof. **Sonia Fiorilli** (Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy)

Talk title: “Smart nanobiomaterials and 3D fabrication technologies to face osteoporosis: the challenge of the GIOTTO project”

(<https://www.giottoproject.eu/>)

3. **Joshua Kaggie** (Department of Radiology, University of Cambridge, UK)
Talk title: “Advanced imaging and stem cell tracking: a transversal enabling technology”
(<http://starstem.eu/project/project-posters/>)

The event was virtually held, as reported in the announcement on the Congress website.

Figure 1: Announcement of the 47th ESAO Congress on the conference website.

Figure 2 shows the slide used to introduce the Webinar.

September 11, 2021 – Track 3
Symposium:
Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissue regeneration

Luigi Ambrosio
National Research Council
(Naples, Italy)
Biomaterials for osteoarticular tissues regeneration: from basic research to the clinics

Leonardo Ricotti
Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
(Pisa, Italy)
Smart materials and ultrasound for cartilage healing: the ADMAIORA project

Sonia Fiorilli
Politecnico di Torino
(Turin, Italy)
Smart nanobiomaterials and 3D fabrication technologies to face osteoporosis: the challenge of the GIOTTO project

Joshua Kaggie
University of Cambridge
(Cambridge, UK)
Advanced imaging and stem cell tracking: a transversal enabling technology

Figure 2: Presentation slide for the Workshop on “Biomaterials, stem cells and enabling technologies for osteoarticular tissue regeneration”.

A few slides regarding the ADMAIORA-related talk are reported in the following.

September 11, 2021

Symposium:
Biomaterials, stem cells
and enabling technologies
for osteoarticular tissue
regeneration

Smart materials and ultrasound for cartilage healing: the ADMAIORA project

Leonardo Ricotti

(leonardo.ricotti@santannapisa.it)

Regenerative Technologies Lab
The BioRobotics Institute

Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (Pisa, Italy)

ADMAIORA targets a novel paradigm for cartilage regeneration

PCT patent: L. Ricotti, et al. "Material and system for the therapeutic treatment of joints". No. WO2020/174395. Priority date: 25/02/2019

Development of nanocomposite hydrogels

VitroGel

Alginate-like biomaterial

Mixing of all components and waiting for for 20 min (ionic gelation)

Methacrylated gellan gum

LED
18 mW/cm²
30 s

+ 50 µg/mL BaTiO₃
+ 25 µg/mL GO
+ 2 million cells/mL

Ultrasound stimulation: “engineering the process”

Low frequency (~ 38 kHz)

High frequencies (500 kHz – 5 MHz)

PCT patent: F. Fontana, et al. “Cell culture support for controlled ultrasonic stimulation”. No: WO2021/014331. Priority date: 23/07/2019

Acknowledgments

Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (Grant Agreements No. 814413 and 853995)

ADMAIORA

The number of participants was not available, being the symposium held on a virtual platform. However, the ESAO Conference is an international reference event for the community of researchers working in the field of artificial and bioartificial organs, regenerative medicine and medical devices. The Symposium thus surely targeted a vast number of persons.

3.2 Live Webinar on Osteoarthritis and Arthritis organized by AMRER – non-technical workshop

An online (Facebook and Youtube) webinar was organized by A.M.R.E.R., an Italian association of rheumatic patients, on 12th October, 2021. Here, experts in the field presented the last news in the treatment of osteoarthritis and arthritis, research with stem cells and ultrasound and pain management.

During the event, Prof. Riccardo Meliconi, Dr. Gina Lisignoli and Dr. Alessandro Russo from Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli and Dr. Andrea Cafarelli from the Institute of BioRobotics spoke about the ADMAIORA project and the new challenges regarding the treatment of osteoarthritis to a broad audience.

Here is the link to the webinar, which was seen by approximately **2700 people**.

<https://fb.watch/8CFZrvf56r/>

Figure 3. Live webinar on Osteoarthritis and Arthritis organized by A.M.R.E.R.

4 Other key communication events

4.1 TV interview on SuperQuark – RAI: Italian State Broadcaster

On 14th July, 2021, the Project Coordinator Prof. Leonardo Ricotti was interviewed at "SuperQuark", the most important Italian program focused on scientific dissemination. The main topic of the interview was the ADMAIORA vision and technology, the associated challenges to fight osteoarthritis and the enormous benefits that it may bring in the future on both direct and indirect costs for the European healthcare systems.

2.263.000 people (13% share of the Italian TV audience on that day) have seen the TV show.

The full interview (in Italian) is available on Youtube at this link:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OL-O_Ky6wAM

This video received **11.800 views**.

Figure 4. Interview to Prof. Leonardo Ricotti – SuperQuark – 14/07/2021

4.2 ADMAIORA @ Olympic games of Tokyo 2021

A Video presenting the Admaiora project and his link with the sports world was prepared in collaboration with the Italian Olympic Committee (CONI) and shared during the Olympic games of Tokyo 2021 at Casa Italia.

The video in the English version is available at the following link:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/ca65sptmxdm45lg/ADMAIORA_CONI_ENG.mp4?dl=0

Casa Italia was populated by many athletes and media professionals during the Olympic games. The video thus had a broad international visibility, on those days.

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ITALIA

CASA TOKYO2020

Figure 5. Screenshots of the video shared during the Olympic games of Tokyo 2020.

4.3 TEDx Talk- LungarnoMediceo

On 12th September, 2021 the Project Coordinator Prof. Leonardo Ricotti was invited in the first edition of the TEDxLungarnoMediceo event in Pisa.

During his talk “*Migliorare la vita grazie alla bioingegneria*” Prof. Ricotti described to a large audience how bioengineering could improve - in a rapidly aging society - the quality of life of a large number of patients suffering from serious pathologies, such as osteoarthritis.

The talk is available on YouTube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wvivrqODZQ> (views: **1580**)

Figure 6. TEDx Talk - LungarnoMediceo

5 Conclusions

This Deliverable describes the key dissemination and communication events organized during the third year of the ADMAIORA project. In particular:

- A scientific workshop held at ESAO;
- A live Webinar on Osteoarthritis and Arthritis organized by A.M.R.E.R. and directed to patients, in which IOR and SSSA team participated;
- The TV interview on SuperQuark – RAI: Italian State Broadcaster, which reached ~ 2 million people;
- A joint collaboration with CONI during the Olympic games of Tokyo 2020;
- A talk at the TEDxLungarnoMediceo event, in Pisa.

Overall, these events, together with other initiatives, guaranteed excellent visibility of the ADMAIORA project approach and results in both the scientific community and the general population.